

Port Site Complications in Laparoscopic Surgeries in a Tertiary Healthcare Centre

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Abstract:

Background: There is increase in number of laparoscopic surgeries because of lesser complications and rapid patient recovery. Still complications such as port sites infections, port site incision hernia, metastasis etc is occurring. So this study tries to find out the risk factors associated with port site complications.

Material and Methods: A hospital based prospective study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur. Detail socio-demographic characteristics were noted, physical examination was done and port site complications were noted and their relationship was found out.

Results: Most of the port site complications were port site infections. Higher age, obesity and presence of co-morbidity in form of diabetes were associated with significantly higher port site complications compared to lower age, normal BMI and absence of co-morbidity respectively. ($p < 0.05$). Even using 10mm port was associated with more port site hernia and bleeding compared to when 5mm port was used. ($p = 0.05$).

Conclusion: Higher age, higher BMI and presence of co-morbidity is associated with more port site complications. Strict control of blood sugar and blood pressure and developing expertise may reduce incidences of port site complications.

Keywords: Laparoscopic surgeries, incision hernia, diabetes, obesity

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Introduction

The advancement of medical science has achieved a great success in not only providing a skilled surgical intervention but also reducing the morbidity associated with open access surgery and hospital stay. The Laparoscopic surgery which is basically a minimal access surgery uses metallic or disposable plastic trocars to insert through small skin incisions which are called ports. Through these ports telescope, light source and surgical instruments are inserted. Though the complications associated with open access surgeries are reducing, with the increase in number of laparoscopic surgeries the complications such as port sites infections, port site incision hernia, metastasis at the port sites vascular and visceral injuries, air embolism etc has been emerging. [1-3]

Meta analytic study on port site infection revealed that mostly epigastric port (82%) was infected and with *Mycobacterium chelonae* (47%) in laparoscopic cholecystectomy (77%) (most common laparoscopic surgery). The main cause of port site infection was ineffective disinfection of laparoscopic instruments with 2% glutaraldehyde (84%). [4] Even medical condition such as diabetes melli-

tus, hypoalbuminemia, hematologic malignancies and leukopenia are also risk factors for port site infections. [5] Higher preoperative HbA1c levels ($>7.0\%$) was linked to higher surgical site infection mainly for thoracic and lumbar spine surgery [6] even with perioperative hyperglycemia and stress induced hyperglycemia. [7] Data shows Non Tuberculous *Mycobacterium* (NTM) as cause of port site infections with frequencies of 1%-8% reported mostly in India [8].

So, this study tries to add data to the literature regarding port site complications associated with laparoscopic surgery and also studies the risk factors such as diabetes, low immunity etc which may cause increase in risk of port site infection. So the main objective of the study is:

1. To study the port site complications associated with laparoscopic surgery.
2. To study the risk factors associated with port site complications.

Material and Methods

A hospital based prospective study was conducted in the Department of General Study Dr BS Kushwah Institute of Medical Sciences, Kanpur. A total of 100 patients of age 18 to 65 yrs of age who were posted for laparoscopic surgery and given consent for surgery were selected by simple random sampling. Those patients who didn't gave consent, who were not fit for anesthesia and whose surgery was later converted to open surgery were excluded.

Detailed medical history of the study subjects including co morbidity were documented and detail examination was done. Laboratory investigations, including routine blood parameters, WBC count etc were etc were evaluated. Post surgical

complications were documented in number and type of infections, post-surgical bleedings etc. Entire data was compiled in MS Excel Sheet and then entered in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 16.0 for Windows (SPSS, Inc, Chicago, IL, USA). Suitable analysis was done by cross tabulations, correlation analysis etc via SPSS software. Results were described using Chi square test and considered significant if p value found to be less than 0.05.

Results

In this study the mean age of the study subject was 48.36 yrs (SD 11.17) with majority belong to age group 51-60 yrs (47%). There were 43 males and 57 females with female to male ratio 1.32:1.

Table 1. Distribution of study subject according to BMI, Co-morbidity, WBC count, Type of surgery and Port site complications. (N=100)

Variable		Frequency	Percent
BMI (Kg/Sqm)	Normal BMI	68	68.0
	Pre-Obese	22	22.0
	Obese	10	10.0
Co-Morbidity	No Co-morbidities	75	75.0
	Diabetes	14	14.0
	HTN	10	10.0
	COPD	1	1.0
WBC Count (Cells/micro-L)	<=10000	33	33.0
	>10000	67	67.0
Type Of Surgery	Lap Cholecystectomy	39	39.0
	Lap Hernia Repair	22	22.0
	Lap Appendicectomy	19	19.0
	Diagnostic Laparoscopy	8	8.0
	Lap Fundoplication	4	4.0
	Lap Nephrectomy	4	4.0
	Lap Prostatectomy	2	2.0
	Rectopexy	2	2.0
Port Site Complication	No Complications	94	94.0
	Hernia	2	2.0
	Infection	3	3.0
	Bleeding	1	1.0
Total		100	100.0

As shown in the table1. above 68 (68%) patients were having normal BMI and rest 22(22%) and 10 (10%) were pre obese and obese respectively. In this study 75 (75%) were having no co-morbidities and rest 14(14%), 10(10%) and 1(1%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension and COPD

respectively. About 33(33%) were having WBC count <10000/micro L and rest 67(67%) were having WBC count >10000/micro L of blood with mean WBC count to be 11095 (SD 2325).

In this study 39(39%), 22(22%), 19 (19%), 8(8%), 4 (4%), 4(4%),2 (2%) and 2(%) underwent

laparoscopic cholecystectomy, hernia repair, appendectomy, diagnostic laparoscopy, fundoplication, nephrectomy, prostatectomy and rectopexy respectively. Among the study subjects with laparoscopic surgery 94 (94%) did not developed any complications. But again 2(2%) developed port site hernia, 3 (3%) developed port site infection and 1 (1%) developed port site bleeding. So port site infection was the most common complication followed by hernia and bleeding.

In this study out of total 39 patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, 1(2.6%) developed port site hernia and 3 (7.7%) developed port site infection. Out of 4 patients who underwent laparoscopic fundoplication 1 (25%) developed port site bleeding . Rest laparoscopic surgery did not developed any complications. Again out of 2 patients who underwent laparoscopic fundoplication 1 (50%) developed port site hernia. So this port site complications significantly occurred with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. ($p < 0.001$)

Table 2. Ports site complication according to port size. (n=6)

Type Of Port	Port Site Complications			Total	P
	Hernia	Infection	Bleeding		
5mm	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)	0.05
10 mm	2 (66.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (33.3%)	3 (100.0%)	
Total	2 (33.3%)	3 (50.0%)	1 (16.7%)	6 (100.0%)	

As shown in the table 2. total 6 patients developed port site complications and out of that 3 each, occurred with 5mm and 10mm port. All 3 port site infections occurred with 5mm port and all 2 port site hernia and 1 port site bleeding occurred with 10 mm port. So port site hernia and bleeding was more with bigger port i.e. 10 mm port though not significant ($p = 0.05$).

Table 3. Port site complications according to Age, Gender, BMI, Co-morbidities and WBC count. (N=100)

Variable	Port Site Complications				Total	p	
	No Complications	Hernia	Infection	Bleeding			
Age (yrs)	21-30	10 (100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	10(100.0%)	0.031
	31-40	19(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	19(100.0%)	
	41-50	15(93.8%)	1(6.3%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	16(100.0%)	
	51-60	44(93.6%)	0(0.0%)	3(6.4%)	0(0.0%)	47(100.0%)	
	61-70	6(75.0%)	1(12.5%)	0(0.0%)	1(12.5%)	8(100.0%)	
Gender	Male	42 (97.7%)	1 (2.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	43 (100.0%)	0.367
	Female	52 (91.2%)	1 (1.8%)	3 (5.3%)	1 (1.8%)	57 (100.0%)	
BMI (Kg/sqm)	Normal	67 (98.5%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.5%)	0 (0.0%)	68 (100.0%)	0.000
	Pre-Obese	21 (95.5%)	1 (4.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	22 (100.0%)	
	Obese	6 (60.0%)	1 (10.0%)	2 (20.0%)	1 (10.0%)	10 (100.0%)	
Co-morbidities	Nil	75 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	75 (100.0%)	0.000
	DM	10 (71.4%)	1 (7.1%)	3 (21.4%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (100.0%)	
	HTN	9 (90.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (10.0%)	10 (100.0%)	
	COPD	0 (0.0%)	1 (100 %)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	
WBC Count (cells/microL)	<10000	33 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	33 (100.0%)	0.370
	>10000	61 (91.0%)	2 (3.0%)	3 (4.5%)	1 (1.5%)	67 (100.0%)	
Total		94 (94.0%)	2 (2.0%)	3 (3.0%)	1 (1.0%)	100 (100.0%)	

As shown in the table 3. no port site complications occurred among the age group 21 to 30 and 31 to 40 yrs. Among age group 41-50 yrs 1 (6.3%) developed port site hernia. Three patients developed port site infections and they belonged to

age group 51-60 yrs. Similarly among age group 61-70 yrs 1(12.5%) patient each developed port site hernia and bleeding respectively. So ports site complications occurred in higher age group and

this difference was statistically significant. (p=0.031)

Among males only 1 (2.3%) patient developed port site hernia. Among females 1 (1.8%) patient each developed port site hernia and bleeding and 3(5.3%) developed port site infection. Though out of 6 patients who developed port site complications 5 were females but this difference was not statistically significant.(p=0.367)

In this study among the patients with normal BMI only 1 (1.5%) developed port site infection and among the patients who were pre obese 1(4.5%) developed port site hernia. But among the patients who were obese 1 (10.0%) developed port site hernia, 2(20.0%) developed port site infection and 1(10.0%) developed port site bleeding. So the port site complications were more in obese patients and this difference was statistically significant. (p<0.001) (figure 1)

As shown in the table among the patients with no co-morbidity, no one developed port site

complications. Among the patients with hypertension 1(10%) developed port site bleeding and among the patients with COPD as co-morbidity 1(100%) developed port site hernia. Study subjects having diabetes mellitus as co-morbidity, developed port site infection in 3(21.4%) patients and port site hernia in 1(7.1%) patients. So the port site complications occurred only in those with co-morbidity and that too most in those suffering from diabetes mellitus. (p=0.000) (figure 2.)

The patients in the study with WBC count less than 10000/ micro Liter of blood did not developed any port site complications. But among the study populations with WBC count more than 10000/ micro Liter of blood, 2(3%) developed port site hernia, 3(4.5%) developed port site infection and 1(1.5%) developed port site bleeding. It means all 6 port site complications occurred with study population with WBC count more than 10000/ micro Liter of blood and this difference was not statistically significant (p=0.370)

Figure 1: Cluster bar graph showing port site complications according to BMI

Figure 2: Cluster bar graph showing port site complication according to Co-morbidities

Discussion

Laparoscopic surgery has replaced the open surgeries, due to fact the complication and post operative patient morbidity associated was more in case of later. Not only multiple complications such as incisional hernia, suture site infection, wound dehiscence etc were more with open surgeries but also post operative recovery was delayed and pain was more. Laparoscopic surgery has drastically reduced the drawback of open surgery and post operative recovery time has been drastically reduced. [9] Still in laparoscopic surgery there complication such as air embolism, major damage to vessels, insufficient access, port site hernia, port site bleeding, port site infection etc. This study tried to find out the different port site complications associated with different laparoscopic surgeries and also tried to find out the risk factor associated with it.

In this study the mean age of the study subject was 48.36 yrs (SD 11.17) with majority belong to age group 51-60 yrs (47%). There were 43 males and 57 females with female to male ratio 1.32:1. Here 68 (68%) patients were having normal BMI and rest 22(22%) and 10 (10%) were pre obese and obese respectively. In this study 75 (75%) were having no co-morbidities and rest 14(14%), 10(10%) and 1(1%) were suffering from diabetes, hypertension and COPD respectively. The mean WBC count of study subject was 11095 /micro L (SD 2325).

In this study 39(39%), 22(22%), 19 (19%), 8(8%), 4 (4%), 4(4%),2 (2%) and 2(%) patient underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, hernia repair, appendectomy, diagnostic laparoscopy, fundoplication, nephrectomy, prostatectomy and rectopexy respectively. So most common surgery in our study was laparoscopic cholecystectomy i.e 39% followed by laparoscopic hernia repair i.e 22%.

A study on laparoscopic port related complications done in Lucknow Medical College by Sing et al¹⁰ in 2018 also found the laparoscopic cholecystectomy to be most common lap surgery, done in 92.58% followed by lap appendectomy (9%). Similarly in study on port site complications done at Civil Hospital Ahmadabad by Sharma et al [11] in 2013 found most common surgery lap cholecystectomy (353) followed by lap appendectomy (245). A descriptive study done on laparoscopic port site complications in Kasturba Medical College Mangalore Karnataka by Karthik et al [12] in 2013 also revealed lap cholecystectomy as the most common procedure done 37.9% followed by lap appendectomy done in 30.4%. So overall most studies found the most

common lap procedure to be lap cholecystectomy followed by lap appendectomy.

In our study among the study subjects with laparoscopic surgery 94 (94%) did not developed any complications. But again 2(2%) developed port site hernia, 3(3%) developed port site infection and 1 (1%) developed port site bleeding. So port site infection was the most common complication followed by hernia and bleeding. In this study out of total 39 patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, 1(2.6%) developed port site hernia and 3 (7.7%) developed port site infection. Out of 4 patients who underwent laparoscopic fundoplication 1 (25%) developed port site bleeding. Again out of 2 patients who underwent laparoscopic fundoplication 1 (50%) developed port site hernia. So this port site complications significantly occurred with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. ($p < 0.001$)

A crosssectional study done on port site related complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy by Memon [13] et al in 2018 also revealed the most common port site complications to be infection (6%) followed by bleeding (4%), hernia (1%) and hematoma (1%). Similar to our study Sing et al¹⁰ found the most common port site complication to be infection (1.94%) followed by metastasis (0.32%) and hypertrophied scar (0.32%). Karthik et al¹² also found port site infection to be maximum found in 10 subjects followed by bleeding (4), hernia (1), omental trapping (1) and port site metastasis (1). So overall most common port site complication was infection in most of the studies which is similar to our finding.

In our study among age group 41-50 yrs 1 (6.3%) developed port site hernia. Similarly among age group 51-60 yrs 3 (6.4%) patients developed port site infections. Finally among age group 61-70 yrs 1 (12.5%) patient each developed port site hernia and port site bleeding respectively. So ports site complications significantly occurred in higher age group. ($p < 0.05$) Similar finding was there in a prospective study on port site complications by Kumar et al [14] in 2021 done in Nalanda Medical College and Hospital Patna in which out of all port site infection 10% (10), 30% (30), 40% (40) and 20% (20) occurred in ≤ 20 yrs, 21-40, 41-60 and ≥ 60 respectively. Even most of the incisional hernia i.e 66.67% (2) occurred in 41-60 yrs and 33.33% (1) occurred in ≥ 60 yrs ($p > 0.05$). Even Singh et al.[10] revealed that among all laparoscopic complications maximum complications i.e 62.50% (5) occurred in 41-50 age group indicating most of the complications occurring in older age group i.e 41-70 ($p > 0.05$). But Hegde Y et al [15] did not found statistical significant difference between occurrence of laparoscopic port site complications among

different age group ($p = 0.18$). So similar to our study higher age is associated with higher complication and this may be due to fact the older age group has lax muscle tone and increase number of comorbidity.

In our study among males only 1 (2.3%) patient developed port site hernia. But among females 1 (1.8%) patient each developed port site hernia and bleeding and 3(5.3%) developed port site infection. Though out of 6 patients who developed port site complications 5 were females but this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$)

Kumar et al [14] found significant higher number of port site complications in female (69.23%) compared to males (30.77%) ($p < 0.05$). But Hegde Y et al [15] did not found any gender difference in occurrence of port site complications ($p > 0.05$). Even Karthik et al [12] found out port site complications more in females (11) than males (6) though this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Thus we can see there are varied results regarding occurrence of port site complications in both gender and gender seems to do not influence the occurrence of port site complications.

In our study 4 port site complications occurred in obese subject with 2 (20%) developing port site infection and 1(10%) each developing port site hernia and bleeding. Rest in normal BMI subjects only 1 (1.5%) developed port site infection and in pre obese subjects 1(4.5%) developed port site hernia. So the port site complications were more in obese patients and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Hubbali et al [16] found out that out of 5 port site infection, 3 (60%) occurred in over weight group ($p = 0.0402$), out of 2 port site hernia all (100%) occurred in over weight group ($p = 0.0411$) and out of 2 port site hemorrhage all (100%) occurred in over weight group ($p = 0.0411$) and this difference was statistically significant stressing upon the occurrence of port site complications in obese group and obesity being a risk factor of port site complications. Our study also have the same finding . But Kumar et al [14] did not found significant difference ($p > 0.05$) of occurrence of port site complications in normal BMI (5), over weight (5) and obese group (3). On contrast Singh et al [10] found port site complications more among underweight (19.54%) and patients with normal nutritional status (72.85%) compared to overweight ($p > 0.05$) though not statistically significant but showing a contrast feature opposite our. A review of literature regarding ports site infections done by Sasmal et al [8] found out that obesity have no effect on the rate of port site infections following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. So in most of the studies the BMI do not have an influence on port

site complications but our study added that with increase in BMI port site complications increases.

In our study no port site complications occurred with study subjects with no co-morbidities. Those study subject with diabetes developed port site infection in 3(21.4%) patients and port site hernia in 1(7.1%) patients. Among the patients with hypertension 1(10%) developed port site bleeding and among the patients with COPD as co-morbidity 1(100%) developed port site hernia. So the port site complications occurred only in those with co-morbidity and that too most in those suffering from diabetes mellitus. ($p < 0.001$)

Our study finding co relates with other study as done by Kumar et al [14] in which 61.54% (8) port site complications occurred in diabetic subject compared to 38.16% (5) in non-diabetic subject. Singh et al [10] also found similar finding of port site complications among diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic patients i.e 11.54% and 0.78% respectively and this association was found statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). A study by Hubbali et al ¹⁶ also showed that co-morbidities like diabetes mellitus, hypertension, have been found to be significantly associated with the development of port-site complications, especially in seroma formation (0.0001) and bleeding." (p -value < 0.0132) which is similar to our finding. So co morbidities specially diabetes do have a significant influence on occurrence of port site complications specially port site infections.

In our study out of total 6 port site complications all 3 port site infections occurred with 5mm port and all 2 port site hernia and 1 port site bleeding occurred with 10 mm port. So port site hernia and bleeding was more with bigger port i.e 10 mm port though not significant ($p = 0.05$) Similarly Kumar et al [14] found that all the port site complications were observed when 10mm port size was used (10 port site infections and 3 port site incisional hernia). In their review article by Venkatesh Phulle et al ¹⁷ described that as the size of the trocar increases the chance of development of port site hernia increases. study Karthik et al [12] also reported postoperative herniation/entrapment of the omentum from the site of umbilical (camera) port and late (3 months post surgery) herniation of the omentum from the umbilical port site scar (port site hernia) were associated with 10 mm ports. In our study too port site hernia occurred more with 10mm port. So we can say larger size port is a risk factor for hernia.

Conclusion

Laparoscopic surgery has brought down complications associated with open surgeries and also reduced the post op morbidity of the patients. Still complications associated with laparoscopic surgeries may occur in form of port site

complications. In our study higher age being a non modifiable risk factor was associated with more port site complications. Most of the port site complications were port site infections that primarily occurred in patients with diabetes as co morbidity. Since diabetes being a risk factor of infection, strict peri-operative blood sugar control using insulin preparation can reduce incidences of port site infections. Obese patients suffered more from port site hernia, infection and bleeding compared to other group. So expertise must be developed while operating obese patients and moreover strict control of co-morbidities in form of diabetes, hypertension, COPD etc will prevent such complications. Moreover using 5mm port instead of 10 mm port in laparoscopic surgeries may prevent incidences of hernia and bleeding.

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